

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

INTEGRATED MANAGEMENT SYSTEM AS PERSPECTIVES AND OPPORTUNITIES

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Abstract

In the modern world, the integration of markets, even entire economies of various countries, is increasingly manifested and, as a result, the exchange of goods, services, knowledge, and cultural values are becoming increasingly interconnected. In order to function comfortably in such an environment, to ensure an appropriate level of competitiveness, modern organizations must work according to generally established rules. In this article main principles of modern integrated management systems are described in the concept of effective organizational operations.

Keywords: management system, process, natural resources, infrastructure, corporate culture, personnel motivation system, organizational culture, enterprise development.

As it is known, for more than 25 years, many countries have successfully applied in their practice international standards for management systems, the most popular of which are ISO 9001 "Quality management systems. Requirements", ISO 14001 "Environmental Management Systems. Requirements and guidance for use", ISO 27001 "Information technology. Security methods. Information security management systems. Requirements", ISO 45001 (formerly OHSAS 18001) "Occupational safety and health management system. Requirements and guidance for use", ISO 50001 "Energy management systems. Requirements and guidelines for use. All of the above standards are voluntary and companies make their own decisions about their implementation. By ensuring the integration of two and / or more standards into the practice of activity, the management system, accordingly, becomes integrated. All management system standards regulate the requirements for the application of the PDCA Continuous Improvement Cycle (Plan - Do - Check - Improve) [1]. Through the implementation of this cycle by employees and structural divisions, the management is able to ensure control and completeness of the execution of production tasks, timely adjustment of the planned activities with a consistently high level of quality of products and / or services provided. By implementing several standards at the same time, the organization combines their requirements and forms an integrated management system.

Enterprises that have implemented modern management tools are able to increase productivity, respectively, reduce costs, increase customer satisfaction and, as a result, increase economic efficiency and competitiveness. At the same time, it is necessary to realize that four mandatory components are characteristic of any organization's management system: 1) employees; 2) processes; 3) organizational or corporate culture and 4) infrastructure or, in other words, means of work. Improving the management system, it is necessary to design and implement changes in all four listed components. The synergy of all mandatory organizational components allows the company to reach a fundamentally new qualitative level.

When we talk about employees, first of all, functional duties should be formulated and official powers, rights, and responsibilities should be defined. The development of an optimal organizational structure is the logical conclusion of organizational decisions in this part. At this stage, the management of the enterprise must decide which organigram, linear-functional, matrix or divisional, will ensure the normal functioning and development of the company. Much depends on the types of activities of the organization, its scale, business geography and the choice of the appropriate situational management model, which will directly affect the organizational culture of the enterprise. It is important to note that it is advisable to take into account all the multifactorial nature of issues that affect the development of personnel.

It is necessary to develop a transparent and fair system of motivation so that each employee understands what needs to be striven for, what result and in what time frame is expected from him. It is possible to use, for example, a monthly, both collective and individual system for assessing the performance of employees, their combined use, or separately. The following systemic motivation factors can be distinguished: financial, professional, social, the use of which is also allowed jointly or separately.

The financial factor of motivation is aimed at increasing the interest of employees in achieving the goals and objectives set, making the most efficient use of working time. Such a factor is a bonus part of the remuneration and is directly related to the assessment of the achievement by an employee / group of employees of Key Performance Indicators. The financial factor of motivation is paid differentially, depending on the performance of employees as a percentage of wages. As an example, we can consider a system based on the use of KPI (Key Performance Indicators), but not the classical methodology, as a rule, used in evaluating the activities of top management, but a variant of the operational, monthly assessment of the activities of structural units represented by line managers. First of all, it should be noted that before the active use of ISO standards in the post-Soviet space, such concepts as Efficiency and Efficiency, as a rule, were not differentiated,

however, in business terms generally accepted at the world level, these concepts are separated, Efficiency is everything what is associated with the cost of resources (time, money, people, energy costs, etc.) for a certain period of time, and Performance, as a rule, has a quantitative expression (units, percentages, etc.) [1].

The professional motivation factor is aimed at the constant self-improvement of the employee, the desire to improve their skills, professional and career growth, the development and realization of creative potential. The professional motivation factor is a constant, rated value and is paid in the form of a regular bonus to wages for the professional achievements of an employee, based on the results of the next certification and assignment of a qualification category to him. Separately, in the form of one-time monetary bonuses, constructive proposals from employees are encouraged to increase productivity and reduce the costs of production processes.

The social factor of motivation is aimed at meeting the social needs of the employee, recognizing his achievements, forming and developing corporate values. The social factor of motivation is expressed in meeting the social needs of employees, in the form of additional social guarantees, starting with the provision of food, delivery to work and home by company vehicles, medical insurance and ending with the provision of company housing, etc., partially or completely at the expense of the organization, including moral encouragement of employees. When assigning social motivation, it is advisable to take into account the work experience of the employee in the company.

The next mandatory component of the life of an organization, which will be considered in the context of

this article, is management, main and auxiliary business processes. In fact, any process is a clearly described technological sequence of activities, when the main tasks of such processes are to ensure the predictability of its results, both in terms of resource costs and in terms of ensuring the achievement of mandatory qualitative and quantitative indicators.

When considering and analyzing the organization's activities from the point of view of the process approach, it becomes obvious that it is the process approach that allows achieving predictable results, ensures the transparency of the transformation process, and reduces the variability of performance results. From the point of view of development, organizations that apply the process approach, in order to ensure maximum customer satisfaction, standardize their activities, and when market priorities change, they are ready for operational optimization / adaptation of business processes, thereby ensuring stable competitiveness and continuous development.

It is advisable to start with the algorithmization of business processes, which will allow you to look at the technology of carrying out activities from the outside, determine the "inputs" and "outputs" of processes, clearly understand and appoint "owners" of processes, see the relationships at the operational and linear levels, bring some clarity and understanding which processes are duplicated by different employees are unnecessary, ensure the formalization (standardization) of the business process. Below, in Figure 1, the Model of the organization's management system from the point of view of the process approach [2] is shown.

Figure 1. Organizational management system model [2].

At the heart of improving business processes is the task of optimizing them in order to reduce cycle time through the use of advanced technologies, robotization / automation, the introduction of such lean management tools as:

Value Stream Mapping to identify and optimize (eliminate/minimize time) processes that do not add value;

✓ the use of the "Pull" cascade system, in which the internal supplier, who is ahead of its internal consumer in terms of production technology, or the organization itself, in relation to the external client, does nothing until he informs him about it;

✓ visual management, which provides visibility into work in progress, cost levels and areas of competence of employees, determines and visually presents work priorities, daily process performance indicators,

creates favorable conditions for communication in the work area, as well as between management and staff;

- ✓ application in the work of a production cell with a continuous flow, through which production operations are carried out in a clear technological sequence, without interruptions / downtime;

- ✓ the use of SMED (Single Minute Exchange of Die) technologies - quick changeover of equipment, literal translation: "Change of the die in 1 minute", allows you to reduce the time spent on excess production, which is expressed in the fact that more products are produced than required, or earlier than required by the customer and / or internal consumer, respectively, those resources that could be spent on improving quality are spent on increasing the quantity [3].

In recent years, the concept of "corporate culture" is not used only by the lazy. Of course, the initiator of creating a model of corporate culture should be the first manager or owner of the company. As a rule, a typical owner of a domestic small / medium-sized business created his company on a whim, without using calculations, feasibility studies, business plans or development strategies, often using the Napoleonic rule: "The main thing is to get involved in battle, and the war plan will show ...". Therefore, at the past stage there was no time, and often no knowledge, to create and develop a unique culture of relationships that characterize the company in relation to internal (employees) and external (suppliers, customers, partners) parties. In such conditions, in organizations there is a conditional differentiation of employees into management and other employees, who by default are perceived as "low-skilled" personnel, while being the main production personnel. The turnover rate of the main production personnel in such organizations, as a rule, is 100%. By management, the bulk of employees, by default, are perceived as loafers and loafers. Quite consciously, repressive management is used, when, when inconsistencies in work are identified, the question is immediately raised: "Who is to blame"? and the punishment mechanism is activated. Under such conditions, the company suffers irretrievable losses of time, ideas, opportunities for improvement and gaining experience due to such an attitude towards employees, while it is obvious that the organization always incurs losses when employees leave, taking with them the acquired knowledge and experience. First of all, the management of the organization must realize that the attitude towards employees, methods of personnel management come from the first head. It is the first manager, who today, often, concurrently, is also the owner of the business, must realize the importance and responsibility for determining the corporate culture in his organization, which includes a system of values and relationships in the team, creates a psychological and moral climate, forms the company's business philosophy according to relation to internal and external parties. It is very important to realize that the consumer can be both internal and external. In other words, these are not only buyers of the final product / service produced by the organization (external consumer), but also any of your work colleagues (internal consumer) to whom you transfer the results of your work. It is important to strive to create a harmonious internal business environment of the company, in which colleagues are focused

on each other, and all together show an increased interest in the achievements of the organization as a whole.

By definition, infrastructure is a system that includes facilities, equipment and services necessary for the activities of an organization [1]. In fact, without the creation of an infrastructure of a certain level, the start of any activity is not possible. Therefore, it is safe to say that in one form or another the infrastructure takes place in every operating organization.

Depending on the specifics of the company's activities, the set of infrastructure elements also changes. So, manufacturing enterprises have such infrastructural components as: production workshops, repair, tool, transport services, warehouses, production areas, etc. For companies providing intellectual services, software and communication facilities will be mandatory components of the infrastructure. For service organizations, these are specialized premises equipped with the necessary technological and interior equipment, etc. As a rule, at the stage of creating a company, the focus is on infrastructure, because, without the availability of appropriate buildings, structures, premises, equipment, tools, transport, communications, etc. it is simply not possible to carry out this or that activity. However, it is necessary to realize that the infrastructure, like other mandatory components of life, at one or another evolutionary stage of the organization must be purposefully optimized and improved, including:

- a) elimination of unscheduled and development of preventive maintenance;
- b) optimization of warehouse stocks and reduction of costs for maintenance of warehouses;
- c) optimization of the use of production space;
- d) cost optimization for consumables, etc.

Separately, we should mention such an important infrastructural component inherent in any organization as information. Given current trends and the dynamics of scientific and technological progress, in order to consistently improve the infrastructure, it is necessary to focus on information management, which plays a paramount role in the modern business world. It is important to constantly expand and develop hardware, software, system tools and technologies that ensure the creation, storage, processing and use of information, while the speed of response to changes should be equal to the speed of the Internet.

Summing up, we can confidently say that a modern organization that seeks to achieve success in a particular segment of the economy must realize that changes, in order to ensure compliance with the constantly changing requirements of the market, are a natural component of modern times, but must itself, in - firstly, be ready to quickly adapt, and secondly, strive to create a new product that anticipates the wishes of consumers.

References

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